

per haploid genome. A 16-kb genomic clone isolated from a Co 39 genomic library was found to contain three copies of the MAG-7 gene (named rice PR-10a, rice PR-10b, and rice PR-10c). Rice PR-10a, sequenced in its entirety, including about 1.4 kb of the 5' promoter region, shared 100% homology with the MAG-7 cDNA. The rice PR-10b and PR-10c genes have been partially sequenced.

We constructed gene-specific probes to observe transcriptional differences among the three rice PR-10 genes in Northern blots of total RNA isolated from Co 39 seedling leaves at 0, 12, 18, 24, 36, 48, 72, and 144 h after *M. grisea* infection (Fig. 1).

Transcripts of rice PR-10a were induced from a low basal level within 12 h following *M. grisea* infection, with increasing accumulation overtime. *M. grisea* also enhanced transcripts of rice PR-10b, for which induction became strongly visible 48 h after inoculation. Unlike rice PR-10a and rice PR-10b, rice PR-10c exhibited no signs of induction by *M. grisea* in RNA samples isolated from infected rice leaves throughout the 144 h.

Tissue prints of *M. grisea*-infected Co 39 leaves were made using the PR-10a gene-specific probe (Fig. 2). Hybridization of the rice PR-10a probe occurred only at the infection site, illustrating that *M. grisea* induces the rice PR-10a transcript in a localized fashion.

2. Tissue print illustrating the localized transcription of the rice PR-10a gene during *Magnaporthe grisea* infection. A 2-wk-old (Co 39) rice seedling was inoculated with two adjacent 20- μ l drops of *M. grisea* conidial suspension (0.4% gelatin; 1,000 conidia drop⁻¹). Following 72 h of incubation, the seedling was pressed onto a nylon membrane and hybridized to an antisense RNA probe specific for the rice PR-10a transcript. Inset photo: a 4X magnification of the infection site.

Barley genes encoding class II chitinase, class II β 1,3-glucanase, and Type-I ribosome-inactivating protein (Jach et al 1995) will be introduced into rice via *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* transformation to study their ability to control fungal diseases. Both the rice PR-10a promoter and the constitutively expressed ubiquitin promoter will be used to drive each of these genes; the effectiveness of both promoters will be compared.

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Genes controlling field resistance to blast in Japanese upland rice detected using RFLP markers

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After observing the rapid breakdown of vertical resistance genes to blast, such as *Pi-k*, rice breeders are now developing

breeding lines with field resistance to blast. Field resistance is defined as the resistance that allows effective control of a parasite under natural field conditions. Japanese upland rice varieties are potential gene donors for field resistance. Studies using linkage analysis with conventional genetic markers have pointed to several different loci controlling field resistance to blast (Goto 1970, Shinoda et al 1971, Higashi and Saito 1985).

We studied the chromosomal location of genes controlling field resistance to blast in Japanese upland rice using restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) markers.

RFLP is frequently detected among Japanese varieties. About 40% of RFLP

markers located on the rice genetic linkage map revealed RFLP between lowland and upland rice varieties using DNA probes polymorphic between lowland and upland varieties.

Field resistance to leaf blast was genetically analyzed. Three hundred twelve F₃ lines from a cross between Nipponbare (moderately susceptible, lowland) and Owarihatamochi (resistant, upland) were field-tested for resistance to blast. Of these, 27 F₃ lines expressed resistance equivalent to that of Owarihatamochi while 27 lines were susceptible. Total DNA was extracted from leaves of resistant and susceptible F₃ lines and their parents. Using 138 RFLP markers, we determined the relationship between

Location of the regions (loci) with significant correlation between genotype of RFLP markers and blast field resistance in Japanese upland rice.

markers and resistance/susceptibility in the F_3 lines. We found a close relationship between blast resistance and genotypic frequency in eight regions of six chromosomes. One region was detected each on chromosomes 2, 6, 7, and 12; two regions were detected on chromosomes 4 and 11 (see figure). The loci linked to RFLP markers on chromosomes 4 and 11 played a major role in expressing field resistance, confirming the results of an earlier study (Wang et al 1994).

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Genetic analysis for true resistance to blast in rice varieties

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Analysis of unknown blast resistance gene(s) of introduced or improved indica varieties showing high blast resistance is useful. We estimated the true resistance genes of indica varieties IR50, Suweon 288 (IR24//IR24/IR747), and Takanari (Milyang 42/Milyang 25) using the method of Toriyama et al (1983), in which backcrossed progenies are tested for reactions to blast isolates of different races.

IR50 was crossed with Ouu308, a japonica line having only the *Pi-a* gene. Resulting F_1 plants were backcrossed with parent Ouu308 to obtain B_1F_2 lines. We inoculated 141 lines of the B_1F_2 with blast isolate TH68-141 (race 003, compatible to *Pi-a* only) to estimate the number of true resistance genes involved. The ratio of the B_1F_2 lines fixed for susceptibility to the total B_1F_2 lines tested was 17.0%, indicating that IR50 has two or three true resistance genes, exclusive of *Pi-a* (Table 1). All 24 B_1F_2

Table 1. Expected and actual ratios of B_1F_2 lines fixed for susceptibility to the total B_1F_2 lines tested for different numbers of true resistance genes involved (except for *Pi-a*).

Genes involved (no.)	2	3	4	5	6
Expected ratio	25.0	12.5	6.3	3.1	1.6
Actual ratio					
IR50	17.0				
Suweon 288				3.0	
Takanari		13.0			

Table 2. Blast isolates of different races used and the corresponding true resistance genes.

Isolate (race)	TH 68-141 (003)	Naga 69-150 (007)	NAO -02 (033)	Ina N86-95A (047)	TH 67-106 (103)	Ina 85-101 (303)	5A (403)	TH 87-20 (007-b ⁺)
Compatible gene(s) for true resistance	<i>Pi-a</i>	<i>Pi-a</i> <i>Pi-i</i>	<i>Pi-a</i> <i>Pi-k</i> <i>Pi-k^m</i>	<i>Pi-a</i> <i>Pi-i</i> <i>Pi-z</i>	<i>Pi-a</i> <i>Pi-ta</i>	<i>Pi-a</i> <i>Pi-ta</i> <i>Pi-ta²</i>	<i>Pi-a</i> <i>Pi-z^t</i>	<i>Pi-a</i> <i>Pi-i</i> <i>Pi-b</i>

lines fixed for susceptibility to TH68-141 showed resistance to blast isolate Naga66-16 (race 001, incompatible to *Pi-a* gene), indicating that IR50 has the *Pi-a* gene. We selected 29 of the B_1F_2 lines showing the segregation ratio of 3 resistant: 1 susceptible plants against TH68-141 and inoculated these with seven isolates of different races (Table 2). Of these, eight lines showed susceptibility to isolate TH87-20 (race 007-b⁺, compatible to *Pi-a*, *Pi-i*, and *Pi-b*) despite showing segregation against isolate Naga69-50 (race 007, compatible to *Pi-a* and *Pi-i*). This indicates that IR50 also has the *Pi-b* gene. Based on the response of the lines to other isolates, it was difficult to estimate other true resistance genes in IR50 (Table 2). The results suggest that IR50 has the *Pi-a*, *Pi-b*, and one or two true resistance genes.

Suweon 288 and Takanari were backcrossed with variety Nekken 2, which has the *Pi-a* and *S-5ⁿ* (wide-compatibility gene to reduce hybrid sterility). We inoculated 100 lines of these B_1F_2 with blast isolate TH68-141. The ratio of B_1F_2 lines fixed for susceptibility to the total lines tested were 3.0 and 13.0%, respectively, indicating that Suweon 288 has four to six genes and Takanari has three genes, exclusive of *Pi-a* (Table 1). Both varieties were verified to have the *Pi-a* gene after inoculation with isolate Naga66-16, with 3 and 13 of the B_1F_2 lines fixed for susceptibility to TH68-141, respectively. When seven isolates (Table 2) were used to check 28 and 50 of the B_1F_2 lines showing the segregation against TH68-141 respectively for the two varieties, only Takanari was proven to have the *Pi-b* gene based on the line's response to isolates Naga69-150 and TH87-20. The results suggest that Suweon 288 has *Pi-a* and four to six other genes. Takanari, on the other hand, has *Pi-a*, *Pi-b*, and two other genes.

Some of the genes we failed to identify in this study are probably new resistance genes, including recessive ones.